
The Cybersecurity and AI Nexus in the EU Digital Acquis*

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Table of contents

1. Introduction. – 2. AI for cybersecurity in cybersecurity law. – 3. The tripartite dimension of cybersecurity in the AI Act. – 4. Cybersecurity as a fundamental right? Insights from the AI Act. – 5. Conclusion.

1. Introduction

Cybersecurity has been at the core of numerous legislative initiatives of the European Union in the past years. Growing concerns have more recently emerged regarding its specific role within the broader global context shaped by escalating international conflicts. Increasingly, hybrid warfare - where cyber operations are used alongside conventional military tactics - dominates the international security landscape. Calls to develop risk-measured responses that adequately take these risks into account have increasingly emerged¹, including from institutional actors². However, cybersecurity is not merely a key concept in interstate relations, and thus in the international public law domain; rather, it has gained significant momentum from a regulatory perspective in the context of EU digital law through a variety of legal norms applicable to the private sector, as well as to public authorities.

AI systems process large amounts of information, both during inference and model training, which renders them vulnerable to cybersecurity threats and risks. In addition, AI systems rely on software and hardware, which may be open to software vulnerabilities, as well as input manipulation and poisoning attacks³. At the same time, AI can be used to generate malware

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¹ See for example the discussion on a principle of due diligence in terms of cybersecurity among states: K. Bannelier, *Due diligence as a cardinal principle in the fight against malicious cyber activities*, in A. Segura Serrano (ed.), *Global Cybersecurity and International Law*, London, 2024; A. Coco- T. de Souza Dias, ‘*Cyber Due Diligence: A Patchwork of Protective Obligations in International Law*’, in *European Journal of International Law*, 32(3), 2021, 771 ss.

² B. Buchanan, *The hacker and the state: Cyber attacks and the new normal of geopolitics*, Cambridge (MA), 2020.

³ CEPS, *Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity. Technology, Governance, and Policy Challenges*, Final Report, CEPS Task Force, 2021, 55f.

or automate cyberattacks⁴. Yet, AI does not pose a threat to cybersecurity⁵; it may also serve as part of the solution, by improving system robustness, response, and resilience⁶. Machine learning, for example, can detect cybersecurity vulnerabilities⁷. The interaction between the concepts, applications, and uses of AI and cybersecurity is reflected in the recent EU legal instruments, adopted in the area of cybersecurity and artificial intelligence⁸. Therefore, cybersecurity has clearly emerged as a distinct issue, closely linked to - but separate from - data protection, even though the two aspects remain - in the words of the European Data Protection Supervisor Wojciech Wiewiórowski - «two sides of the same coin»⁹.

It is not by coincidence that cybersecurity stands out as a key principle in the context of the EU AI regulation, in the AI Act¹⁰ (along with data protection). As well-known, building upon its well-established risk-based approach blueprint, the EU wishes to leverage its role as first-mover compared to other jurisdictions in governing the implementation of AI systems in many respects. As AI systems become increasingly popular, adopted by private and public actors in the performance of business activities but also public services, a key question arises: what is the role of cybersecurity in this domain? While data protection is a well-established fundamental right in the EU legal order and has played a pivotal role in shaping of the EU digital acquis¹¹ over the past decade, even gaining the status of ethical key requirement for trustworthy AI systems¹², does the Union legislator regard

⁴ T. Wischmeyer-M. Strecker, *Generative AI and Cybersecurity*, in P. Hacker-A. Engel-S. Hammer-B. Mittelstadt (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of the Foundations and Regulation of Generative AI*, Oxford, 2025.

⁵ T.F. Blauth-O.J. Gstrein-A. Zwitter, *Artificial intelligence crime: An overview of malicious use and abuse of AI*, *IEEE Access*, 10, 2022, 77110 ss.

⁶ CEPS, *Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity. Technology, Governance, and Policy Challenges*, cit.

⁷ A. Calderaro-S. Blumfelde, *Artificial intelligence and EU security: the false promise of digital sovereignty*, in *European Security*, 31(3), 2022, 415 ss.; K. Munonye-M. Péter, *Machine learning approach to vulnerability detection in OAuth 2.0 authentication and authorization flow*, in *International Journal of Information Security*, 21(2), 2022, 223 ss.

⁸ H. Junklewitz-R. Hamon-A. André-T. Evas-J. Soler Garrido-J.I. Sanchez Martin, *Cybersecurity of Artificial Intelligence in the AI Act*, Luxembourg, 2023.

⁹ W. Wiewiórowski, *Cybersecurity and Data Protection: a necessary and powerful duo*, in *European Data Protection Supervisor*, 28 September 2023

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act).

¹¹ See the use of art. 16 TFEU as the legal basis for the adoption of a number of EU law acts, such as the AI Act (along with art. 114 TFEU), the Law Enforcement Directive (Directive (UE) 680/2016), the EUDPR Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC, OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 39–98.

¹² European Commission, *Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI*, in *digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu*, 8 April 2019.

cybersecurity to a comparable status? To answer the question above, we take the AI Act as a litmus test for the growing, yet still underdeveloped role of cybersecurity. We do not ask whether cybersecurity is or should be a fundamental right; rather, we ask if the consideration that cybersecurity receives in the AI Act is conducive to an emerging role - or at least an aspiration - of cybersecurity to have a function similar to that of other fundamental rights in shaping EU policy and law making. We discuss, for example, the similarities that can be observed with the overall impact of data protection in EU digital law.

In the end, we aim to determine if the AI Act promotes a trajectory towards recognising cybersecurity as a fundamental right, evaluating this possibility in light of its various possible interpretations and recent developments in EU law.

The analysis is based on doctrinal legal method, with the aim to offer an understanding of the rationales, design, and main role related to cybersecurity in the AI Act and reflect on the main research question of this work. This paper does not aim to draw an exhaustive analysis of the understanding of cybersecurity in the European Union legal order; rather, its goal is to test the growing legal ambitions of this requirement against the most important of the recent developments in the EU digital acquis, namely the AI Act.

The paper begins by analysing the relationship between AI and cybersecurity in the EU cybersecurity law, taking the Network and Information Security Directive 2 (“NIS2 Directive” or “NIS2”) and the Cyber Resilience Act (“CRA”) as examples, then it will tackle a tripartite dimension of this concept in the AI Act, to assess the extent to which cybersecurity is moving closer to being recognised as a fundamental right that may contribute to shaping future developments in EU law.

2. AI for cybersecurity in cybersecurity law

2.1 Cybersecurity as a regulatory priority in the Union

The 2020 EU’s Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade stressed, among other concerns, that the EU lacks collective situational awareness of cyber threats while many of the critical sectors such as transport, energy, health, and telecommunications depend on network and information security. The Strategy also highlighted that the investigation of almost all crimes involves a digital component and that cybersecurity incidents such as WannaCry ransomware attack have a major impact on the global economy¹³. In the same line, the Europol Internet Organised Crime Assessment 2021 reported an increase in cybercrime-as-a-service, an improvement in the modus-operandi of malware operators, and an overall increase in op-

¹³ Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council, *The EU’s Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade*, JOIN (2020) 18 final, 16.12.2020.

portunities and sophistication¹⁴. The sophistication extends beyond technical tools and methods of the attackers, to include other aspects, such as the sentimental value owners bear for their organisations¹⁵, especially in the case of Smaller and Medium Enterprises.

The 2024 Threat Landscape, published by European Cybersecurity Agency (‘ENISA’) highlights the use of artificial intelligence as an assistant to threat actors, for example for phishing and scripting assistance¹⁶. Since the adoption of the Network and Information Security Directive (NIS), which was the first EU-wide horizontal cybersecurity law¹⁷, and the 2022 NIS2 Directive¹⁸, the European co-legislators have made cybersecurity a clear priority in policy and law-making. The Cybersecurity Act was published in 2019¹⁹, a regulation for a high level of cybersecurity in EU institutions and agencies was published in 2023²⁰ and the Cyber Resilience Act was also adopted one year later²¹. Earlier in 2025, the Cyber Solidarity Act was adopted as a Regulation, aiming at strengthening the capacity in the Union to detect, prepare and respond to cyber threats and incidents²². These are few of the developments in the field, which further underscore the growing commitment of the EU to develop a comprehensive cyberse-

¹⁴ European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation, *Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021*, Luxembourg, 2021.

¹⁵ L.Y. Connolly-D.S. Wall-M. Lang-B. Oddson, *An empirical study of ransomware attacks on organizations: an assessment of severity and salient factors affecting vulnerability*, in *Journal of Cybersecurity*, 6(1) 2020, tyaa023.

¹⁶ ENISA, *ENISA Threat Landscape 2024*, September 2024.

¹⁷ Markopoulou et al. explain that the EU’s interest in cybersecurity was already manifested in 2009 with the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament the Council the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on Critical Information Infrastructure Protection *Protecting Europe from large-scale cyber-attacks and disruptions: enhancing preparedness, security, and resilience* (COM (2009)149). See D. Markopoulou- V. Papakonstantinou-P. De Hert, *The new EU cybersecurity framework: The NIS Directive, ENISA’s role and the General Data Protection Regulation*, in *Computer Law & Security Review*, 35(6), 2019, 105336 ss.

¹⁸ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive), OJ L 333, 27.12.2022.

¹⁹ Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act) OJ L 151, 7.6.2019.

²⁰ Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2023/2841 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 laying down measures for a high common level of cybersecurity at the institutions, bodies, offices and agencies of the Union, OJ L, 2023/2841, 18.12.2023.

²¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013 and (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Cyber Resilience Act) OJ L, 2024/2847, 20.11.2024.

²² Regulation (EU) 2025/38 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 December 2024 laying down measures to strengthen solidarity and capacities in the Union to detect, prepare for and respond to cyber threats and incidents and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/694 (Cyber Solidarity Act) OJ L, 2025/38, 15.1.2025.

curity policy and legal framework²³.

ENISA had defined cybersecurity as the «security of cyberspace, where cyberspace itself refers to the set of links and relationships between objects that are accessible through a generalised telecommunications network, and to the set of objects themselves where they present interfaces allowing their remote control, remote access to data, or their participation in control actions within that cyberspace»²⁴. Later, the Cyber Security Act provided a definition of cybersecurity as «the activities necessary to protect network and information systems, the users of such systems, and other persons affected by cyber threat»²⁵. There are plenty of other definitions on what constitutes cybersecurity²⁶, the existence of which, demonstrates the complexity of cybersecurity as a research area. The taxonomy proposed by the Joint Research Centre shows for example the different aspects that comprise cybersecurity ranging from sectors such as energy, digital services, platforms to telecoms, banks, and others, to domains such as networked and distributed systems, cryptology, assurance, and to use cases and technologies such as AI, disaster resilience, Internet of Things (IoT), fight against crime, and many others²⁷.

Independently of the approach one may choose to adopt as regards the concept and regulation of cybersecurity, it is clear that cybersecurity plays a dual role; it is both an accessory regulatory tool, aimed to protect rights, principles, goods, and values, but also constitutes a regulatory target on its own. For example, cybersecurity is an essential means to protect one's online privacy. At the same time, cybersecurity warrants autonomous protection, since cybersecurity breaches may inflict damages on computer systems and data, and in turn result in financial losses or other operational harms. In ransomware cases, where offenders exploit security vulnerabilities and prevent rightsholders such as hospitals or universities from accessing their systems and data, one understands the individual value of cybersecure environments²¹.

Before delving into the role of cybersecurity in the AI Act, this work examines how EU cybersecurity law regards AI. The focus is on the Network and Information Security Directive 2 and the Cyber Resilience Act, two of the most impactful cybersecurity legal instruments in EU cybersecurity.

²³ At the same time, the EU regulator has acknowledged the complexity of the cybersecurity regulatory environment and the EU digital acquis more generally (including the General Data Protection Regulation and other instruments) and has announced the proposal of amendments aiming at the simplification of obligations and requirements. See European Commission, *A simpler and Portfolio faster Europe: Communication on implementation and simplification*, European Commission 2024-2029.

²⁴ ENISA *Definition of Cybersecurity Gaps and overlaps in standardisation*, v. 1, 2015, 7, available at enisa.europa.eu.

²⁵ Art. 2(1) Cyber Security Act.

²⁶ See overview in V. Papakonstantinou, *Cybersecurity as praxis and as a state: The EU law path towards acknowledgement of a new right to cybersecurity?*, in *Computer Law & Security Review*, 44, 2022, 105653 ss. and in M. Veale-I. Brown, *Cybersecurity*, in *Internet Policy Review*, 9(4), 2020; 1 ss.

²⁷ I. Nai Fovino-R. Neisse-J. Hernandez Ramos- N. Polemi-G. Ruzzante-M. Figwer- A. Lazari, *A Proposal for a European Cybersecurity Taxonomy*, EUR 29868 EN, Luxembourg, 2019.

2.2 AI as a cybersecurity enhancing technology in NIS2

EU cybersecurity law maintains a technology-neutral approach, but in parallel, acknowledges the possible impact of different AI applications on cybersecurity. Two prominent examples are found in the NIS2 Directive and the Cyber Resilience Act²⁸

The NIS2 Directive, which provides cybersecurity risk-management measures and reporting obligations for its regulated entities (essential and important entities) across different sectors²⁹, invites these entities to evaluate their capabilities and pursue “cybersecurity enhancing technologies”, such as AI. Specifically, AI is seen as capable of enhancing the cybersecurity capabilities of essential and important entities, and the security of network and information systems³⁰.

Further, NIS2 invites Member States to encourage the use of AI for the «detection and prevention of cyberattacks»³¹. Another more nuanced use of AI in the framework of NIS2 concerns the power of Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs)³² to provide «proactive scanning of the network and information systems [...] to detect vulnerabilities with a potential significant impact»³³, which may rely on AI, but not necessarily³⁴.

2.3 Cybersecurity requirements for high-risk AI systems in the Cyber Resilience Act

The Cyber Resilience Act, which was adopted in parallel with the AI Act, provides, inter alia, «essential cybersecurity requirements for the design, development and production of products with digital elements», as well as «obligations for economic operators in relation to those products with respect to cybersecurity»³⁵. The products with digital elements, regulated in the CRA, may sometimes include AI applications (e.g. a smart home appliance, which uses a remote biometric identification system), or be classified

²⁸ See more in S. Schmitz-Berndt-M.D. Cole, *Towards an efficient and coherent regulatory framework on cybersecurity in the EU: the proposals for a NIS 2.0 directive and a cyber resilience act*, in *Applied Cybersecurity & Internet Governance*, 1(1), 2022, 1 ss.; N. Vandezande, *Cybersecurity in the EU: How the NIS2-directive stacks up against its predecessor*, in *Computer Law & Security Review*, 52, 2024, 105890 ss.

²⁹ Art. 1(2)(b) NIS2 Directive.

³⁰ Recital 89 NIS2 Directive.

³¹ Recital 51 NIS2 Directive.

³² CSIRTs are designated by Member States and have a range of powers to support inter alia essential and important entities. See further art. 10 NIS2 and I. Kamara-J. van den Boom, *Computer Security Incident Response Teams in the reformed Network and Information Security Directive: Good practices*, National Cybersecurity Centre, 2022.

³³ Art. 11(3)(e) NIS2 Directive.

³⁴ See ENISA, *Proactive Detection Measures and Information Sources*, 2020, available at enisa.europa.eu.

³⁵ Art. 1(b) CRA.

themselves as AI systems³⁶.

For those specific systems, to which both the CRA and the AI Act apply, the CRA provides a dedicated provision, clarifying the applicability of the different requirements and aims at harmonising and cutting red tape, where possible. Art. 12 CRA introduces therefore a presumption of compliance with the requirement for cybersecure high-risk AI systems³⁷. Products with digital elements, which are also high-risk AI systems, are deemed to comply with art. 15 AI Act, when three cumulative conditions are met: First, the products must fulfil the essential cybersecurity requirements of the CRA. Second, the manufacturer of such products has implemented processes that also comply with the essential cybersecurity requirements of the CRA. And third, the product has successfully passed a conformity assessment procedure and is accompanied by a declaration of conformity³⁸.

Overall, the analysed cybersecurity legislation identifies the relevance and interdependence of cybersecurity and the diverse uses of artificial intelligence, and a need for harmonisation and alignment of the legal frameworks. At a conceptual level, while EU secondary cybersecurity law elevates the significance of cybersecurity for the digital market, citizens and society -and may support claims that cybersecurity is a collective good³⁹, serving at times public interests - it does not establish cybersecurity as an individual fundamental right, at least not within the scope of the examined legal instruments⁴⁰.

3. The tripartite dimension of cybersecurity in the AI Act

While the AI Act is certainly not a cybersecurity law, the term “cybersecurity” is mentioned more than fifty times. The significance of a cybersecure AI system is stressed throughout the text of the Act.

Recital 76 provides: «Cybersecurity plays a crucial role in ensuring that AI systems are resilient against attempts to alter their use, behaviour, performance or compromise their security properties by malicious third parties exploiting the system’s vulnerabilities. [...] To ensure a level of cybersecurity appropriate to the risks, suitable measures, such as security controls, should therefore be taken by the providers of high-risk AI systems, also taking into account as appropriate the underlying ICT infrastructure».

As explained in the following sections, the AI Act addresses cybersecuri-

³⁶ See art. 6(2) and Annex III AI Act. Read further: J. Schuett, *Risk management in the artificial intelligence act*, in *European Journal of Risk Regulation*, 15(2), 2024, 367 ss.

³⁷ See further analysis of art. 15 AI Act in section 3 of this paper.

³⁸ Art. 12(1) and art. 43 CRA. An exception to this presumption is established in art. 12(3) CRA for important products with digital elements. See further Annex III CRA.

³⁹ See similar point made in from M. Kianpour-S.J. Kowalski-H. Øverby, *Advancing the concept of cybersecurity as a public good*, in *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, 116, 2022, 102493 ss.

⁴⁰ A.J. Menéndez, *Some elements of a theory of European fundamental rights*, in A.J. Menéndez-E. O. Eriksen (eds.), *Arguing Fundamental Rights*, Dordrecht, 2006, 155 ss.

ty in three dimensions: as a non-functional requirement, as a conformity assessment criterion, and as an organisational measure. These three dimensions are interconnected, as omitting anyone of them would create a gap in the cybersecurity value chain of the AI ecosystem, which includes providers designing and offering AI systems, deployers using the systems, but also entities tasked with monitoring and supervising compliance.

First, cybersecurity is a *non-functional requirement* for high-risk AI systems and general-purpose AI models with a systemic risk. High-risk AI systems must in general fulfil a range of requirements to mitigate risks to health, safety, and fundamental rights⁴¹. In line with art. 15(1) high-risk AI systems must achieve an «appropriate level of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity»⁴². Those essential requirements must be fulfilled during the lifecycle of a high-risk AI system, and thus abide by the principle of security-by-design⁴³. To assess whether an AI system meets the appropriate level of cybersecurity, a security risk assessment is necessary, as mandated in art. 9 AI Act. The AI Act also establishes a transparency requirement, according to which the provider of a high-risk AI system must inform the deployer about the level of cybersecurity of the system and any «known and foreseeable circumstances» that may impact this level of cybersecurity⁴⁴. This transparency obligation essentially forces providers to conduct cybersecurity due diligence.

Despite these safeguards, cybersecurity of AI systems and AI-specific technologies face several challenges, both in terms of operational processes (e.g., adapting existing measures for AI software) and research and development challenges (e.g., defining metrics for AI cybersecurity or AI threat modelling)⁴⁵. To assist providers of AI systems with compliance to the cybersecurity requirement for AI systems and address those challenges, the European Commission issued a standardisation request towards CEN and CENELEC to develop European technical standards, inter alia providing good practices and state-of-the-art solutions in the area of AI cybersecurity⁴⁶. Currently, a European harmonised standard is being devel-

⁴¹ Recital 66 AI Act.

⁴² Art. 15(1) AI Act.

⁴³ During the legislative process, the European Parliament had proposed the insertion of the principles of security-by-design and by-default in the text of art. 15(1), which however was not accepted in the negotiations with the Council. The wording in the final text nevertheless still essentially refers to the very meaning of security-by-design, by requiring high-risk AI systems to «be designed» and implement cybersecurity «[...] throughout their lifecycle».

See proposed amendment 321, Amendments adopted by the European Parliament on 14 June 2023 on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts (COM(2021)0206 – C9-0146/2021 – 2021/0106(COD)).

⁴⁴ Art. 13(3)(b)(ii) AI Act.

⁴⁵ H. Junklewitz-R. Hamon-A. André-T. Evas-J. Soler Garrido-J.I. Sanchez Martin, *Cybersecurity of Artificial Intelligence in the AI Act*, Luxembourg, 2023, 6.

⁴⁶ Commission Implementing Decision of 22.5.2023 on a standardisation request to the European Committee for Standardisation and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation in support of Union policy on artificial intelligence,

oped in response to this request, focusing on organisational and technical solutions aimed at ensuring the cybersecurity of high-risk AI systems over their lifecycle⁴⁷. Additionally, the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) are developing an international standard providing guidance for organisations to address privacy and information security risks in AI systems and machine learning (ML) models⁴⁸.

In the case of general-purpose AI models, cybersecurity is a non-functional requirement only for those AI models that present a systemic risk. Providers of such models are obliged to ensure an adequate level of cybersecurity protection for both the model and the physical infrastructure⁴⁹. As noted by Nolte et al., there is a discrepancy between the required level of cybersecurity for high-risk AI systems and general-purpose models in the AI Act⁵⁰; while for the former an *appropriate* level of cybersecurity is required, for the latter only an *adequate* level is sufficient.

The second dimension of cybersecurity in the AI Act concerns *cybersecurity as a criterion in conformity assessment*. Before entering the internal market, high-risk AI systems are required to undergo a conformity assessment procedure, either in the form of internal control or via a specific competent body (notified body)⁵¹. This *ex-ante* evaluation of high-risk AI systems, inspired by the product safety legislation and the New Legislative Framework (“NLF”), is mandatory for providers of high-risk AI system⁵².

While the essential cybersecurity requirement of art. 15(1) for high-risk AI systems, discussed above, concerns a non-functional requirement of the system, cybersecurity as a conformity assessment criterion concerns whether the system meets the pre-determined appropriate level of cybersecurity. The threshold of acceptable cybersecurity level should be determined based on a range of factors, including the intended use of the system, the associated risks, and the state-of-the-art in cybersecurity controls and measures⁵³.

Third, cybersecurity constitutes a technical and organisational measure for surveillance and other authorities involved in the enforcement of the AI Act⁵⁴. In particular, conformity assessment bodies themselves must adopt

Annex 1, point 8.

⁴⁷ See [Artificial intelligence - Cybersecurity specifications for AI Systems](#), at [cenelec.eu](#).

⁴⁸ [ISO/IEC CD 27091 Cybersecurity and Privacy - Artificial Intelligence - Privacy protection](#).

⁴⁹ Art. 55(1)(d) AI Act.

⁵⁰ H. Nolte-M. Rateike-M. Finck, *Robustness and Cybersecurity in the EU Artificial Intelligence Act*, Proceedings of the 2025 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '25), 2025.

⁵¹ Art. 16(f) AI Act. A notified body is defined as «a conformity assessment body notified in accordance with this Regulation and other relevant Union harmonisation legislation» in art. 3(22) AI Act.

⁵² Read further at [single-market.economy.ec.europa.eu](#); T. de Graaf-G. Veldt, *The AI Act and its impact on product safety, contracts and liability*, in *European Review of Private Law*, 30(5), 2022, 803 ss.

⁵³ See Recital 78 AI Act.

⁵⁴ Art. 78(2) AI Act.

suitable cybersecurity measures to qualify for notification to the European Commission⁵⁵. Cybersecurity as a technical and organisational measure is not a novel requirement, but a necessary one, for both protecting the models and systems under scrutiny, and establishing trust between regulators and the entities they oversee.

The tripartite framing of cybersecurity in the AI Act certainly shapes it as both a condition of a system and a status, which organisational and technical measures must achieve. The fulfilment of the condition requires normative decisions, from the provider of the system, or standardisation bodies and similar entities, tasked to guide compliance through technical standards and other mechanisms. Those normative decisions largely depend on assessments made by those entities, and have therefore been characterised as value-laden,⁵⁶ as they involve choosing which technical solutions better address cybersecurity risks.

4. Cybersecurity as a fundamental right? Insights from the AI Act

To make sense of how cybersecurity is considered in the AI Act, it is worth recalling the ongoing debate on whether cybersecurity constitutes or should constitute a fundamental right⁵⁷. First of all, given the variety of nuances surrounding this concept, we need to determine in which sense we can speak of cybersecurity as a fundamental right.

Cybersecurity has been conceptualised by Papakonstantinou as a *praxis* and as a *state*, whereby the former represents actions and measures and the latter the protected sphere for natural and legal persons⁵⁸. Other scholars frame cybersecurity as a cluster of values, protecting privacy, security, fairness, and accountability⁵⁹, or approach cybersecurity by association to the threats against it⁶⁰.

Any discussion on the possible role of cybersecurity as a fundamental right could perhaps end with a very old-fashioned and frequently claimed argument in the context of digital policy and regulation: can't we consider cybersecurity as a component of the "general" right to security individuals

⁵⁵ Art. 31 AI Act.

⁵⁶ M. Veale-F. Zuiderveen Borgesius, *Demystifying the Draft EU Artificial Intelligence Act—Analysing the good, the bad, and the unclear elements of the proposed approach*, in *Computer Law Review International*, 22(4), 2021, 97 ss.; A. Tartaro, *Value-laden challenges for technical standards supporting regulation in the field of AI*, in *Ethics and Information Technology*, 26(4), 2024, 72; M. Cantero Gamito-C.T. Marsden, *Artificial intelligence co-regulation? The role of standards in the EU AI Act*, in *International Journal of Law and Information Technology*, 32, 2024, eaae011.

⁵⁷ Among others, see P.G. Chiara, *Towards a right to cybersecurity in EU law? The challenges ahead*, in *Computer Law & Security Review*, 53 (2024) 105961.

⁵⁸ V. Papakonstantinou, *Cybersecurity as praxis and as a state*, cit.

⁵⁹ I. van de Poel, *Core values and value conflicts in cybersecurity: beyond privacy versus security*, in *The ethics of cybersecurity*, 2020, 45 ss.

⁶⁰ D. Craigen-N. Diakun-Thibault-R. Purse, *Defining cybersecurity*, in *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 4(10), 2014. See also K. Bannelier-T. Christakis, *Cyber-Attacks—Prevention-Reactions: The Role of States and Private Actors*, Paris, 2017, 86.

already enjoy under the existing constitutions and bills of rights? In other terms, wouldn't it simply work as a "cyber" version of the right to security? As far as the EU legal order is concerned, it is already well known that the Court of Justice has provided a negative answer regarding the coverage afforded by art. 6 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Following the Advocate General's opinion in *La Quadrature du Net I*⁶¹, the Court made it clear that this provision reflects the content of art. 5 of the European Convention of Human Rights, which protects the right to liberty and the right to security; however, the provision aims «to ensure that individuals are protected from arbitrary or unjustified deprivations of liberty» by a public authority⁶²; accordingly, art. 6 of the Charter cannot be interpreted «as imposing an obligation on public authorities to take specific measures to prevent and punish certain criminal offences»⁶³. As noted by the Advocate General, the security in question⁶⁴ is «personal security, concerned with the conditions under which individuals may have their physical freedom restricted, not the public security inherent in the existence of the State, which is an essential prerequisite in a developed society for reconciling the exercise of public powers with the enjoyment of individual rights»⁶⁵. This interpretation already presents a significant obstacle to deriving a concept of cybersecurity as a fundamental right from the existing provisions, given the variety of nuances by which cybersecurity can be characterised.

At the same time, the fact that cybersecurity may come into play as a requirement playing different roles – as noted above – makes it difficult to effectively capture its nature and circumscribe it to a specific constitutional concept: it equally constitutes a condition for individuals to enjoy their privacy but also other fundamental rights. Therefore, the variety of ways in which cybersecurity operates as a requirement, including in the AI domain, suggests why building cybersecurity upon the existing concept of security would only partially reflect the reach and significance of such notion. This does not mean that constitutions or international (or EU) treaties should necessarily incorporate a new formulation of this requirement for it to be substantively recognized as a fundamental right. In other terms, any discussion focused on the need to revisit the wording of existing provisions to modernize their content would be pointless; rather, the key point lies in whether we can speak of cybersecurity using the same fundamental rights "language" in which concepts such as privacy and data protection are used. Therefore, discussing the fundamental right nature of cybersecurity goes far beyond debating whether existing provisions, given their current wording, suffice to protect it. To understand if such

⁶¹ Opinion of Advocate General Sánchez-Bordona, Joined Cases C-511/18, C-512/18, *La Quadrature du Net et al.* (2020), § 95.

⁶² ECJ, Joined Cases C 511/18 Case C 512/18 Case C 520/18, *La Quadrature du Net et al.* (2023), § 125.

⁶³ *Ibidem.*

⁶⁴ More recently, see also the opinion of Advocate General Pikamäe, Case C-118/22 (2023), § 51

⁶⁵ Opinion of Advocate General Sánchez-Bordona, Joined Cases C-511/18, C-512/18, *cit.*, § 99.

nature actually emerges in the EU digital law-making, the AI Act constitutes a litmus test to test the ambitions and aspirations of the concept of cybersecurity

As well-known, scholars have defined the AI Act a «medley of product safety legislation and fundamental rights» protection⁶⁶. Concerns for fundamental rights protection received a far from consistent consideration in the legislative process of the AI Act⁶⁷, which brought to light the possible varying understanding of AI as a product but also as a source of risks and opportunities alike. While protection of fundamental rights emerged as a pivotal concern before European Parliament, the text eventually voted as result of the Trilogue has commonly been seen as a compromise, and sometimes criticized as an ineffective paradigm⁶⁸ which ultimately risk undermining fundamental rights protection. Against these discussions regarding the actual degree of protection that the AI Act offers for fundamental rights, the role of cybersecurity within its broader architecture has to be discussed in light of its tripartite nature as described above. Is it merely a component, albeit important, of product safety legislation or can it aspire to a broader consideration as part of a fundamental right requirement? We conduct this analysis by observing some analogies in the language of a key piece of legislation with a clear fundamental rights-driven nature, like the General Data Protection Regulation (“GDPR”)⁶⁹.

On one hand, the current wording of art. 15 AI Act resembles to a certain extent that of art. 5 GDPR, by setting forth some basic principles such as accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity. Para. 1 requires high-risk AI systems to be designed and developed in order to meet an appropriate level of these requirements and so that they perform consistently throughout their lifecycle. The wording of this provision also recalls the language of the data protection by design principle as shaped by art. 25 GDPR and, albeit indirectly, that of art. 32 of the GPDR, which requires the adoption of adequate organisational and technical measures in light of the inherent level of risk of the processing activities. However, while the data protection by design seems to lay down a near-universal principle applicable regardless of the level of risk posed by processing activities, art. 15 AI Act is framed as a requirement binding on high-risk AI systems only. This means that the requirement does not apply to AI systems other than high-risk ones, which indirectly reveals that accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity are not mandatory outside the high-risk specific domain,

⁶⁶ N. Petit-M. Almada, *The EU AI Act: A Medley of Product Safety and Fundamental Rights?*, Robert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies Research Paper No. 2023_59; see also see P.G. Chiara, *Understanding the regulatory approach of the Cyber Resilience Act: protection of fundamental rights in disguise?*, in *European Journal of Risk Regulation*, 2025, 1 ss.

⁶⁷ F. Palmiotto, *The AI Act Roller Coaster: The Evolution of Fundamental Rights Protection in the Legislative Process and the Future of the Regulation*, in *European Journal of Risk Regulation*, 2025, 1 ss.

⁶⁸ M. Almada-A. Radu, *The Brussels side-effect: how the AI Act can reduce the global reach of EU policy*, in *German Law Journal*, 25(4), 2024.

⁶⁹ Regulation (UE) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC.

when one considers solely the AI Act. The limited scope of application of these requirements weakens cybersecurity consideration in a fundamental rights fashion. Para. 2 also establishes that the Commission shall define the relevant performance metrics to measure, among other things, the appropriate levels of accuracy and robustness. The remaining provisions set forth in art. 15 are not conducive of a different evaluation. Indeed, they specify the requirement of resilience and impose the adoption of technical and organisational measures for this purpose. In this respect, some convergences can be observed comparing once again the AI Act to the GDPR, most notably to the extent the latter, pursuant to art. 32, requires controllers and processors to «implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk» in light of a variety of factors, namely «the state of the art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risk of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons». This is not necessarily connected to a fundamental right-based understanding of cybersecurity (which, strictly speaking according to the language of the AI Act, is only one of the three requirements laid down for high-risk AI systems by art. 15); rather, it highlights that, for the purposes of the AI Act, cybersecurity does not merely reflect (nor does it correspond to) the need to ensure an adequate level of data protection. If the principle of data protection by design were enough, the AI Act would not specify the requirements under art. 15, which go beyond compliance with the GDPR principles. This is a more complex and encompassing requirement, which applies regardless of the existence of data processing activities and implies the need of additional safeguards than the ones implemented pursuant to the GDPR. However, while defining such requirement the AI Act seems to employ more the language of product safety legislation rather than that of fundamental rights-driven legislation. So, the language of the AI Act does not support any findings on a supposed nature of cybersecurity as a fundamental right; at the same time, its specific shaping of the risk-based approach leads to considering cybersecurity, together with accuracy and robustness, as a binding set of requirements only when it comes to high-risk AI systems, therefore implicitly downgrading its value as fundamental right. If cybersecurity were to be treated as a requirement stemming from the existence of such a fundamental right, it would be difficult to reconcile this understanding with the limited scope of art. 15 AI Act, which applies only to high-risk AI systems. While the AI Act acknowledges the importance of cybersecurity and incorporates it in the regulation of AI, the regulation does not significantly enhance its value - at least not to the extent that would reflect its recognition as a fundamental right. This should not come as surprise, in the end, given that the AI Act does not posit itself as a piece of legislation that is genuinely driven by the protection of fundamental right.

5. Conclusion

The trajectory drawn in this article illustrates how cybersecurity has evolved into a regulatory priority, becoming a *sine qua non* requirement for a variety of actors and domains, namely for data-driven systems, critical infrastructures as well as for providers of essential and vital services. The specific developments in EU cybersecurity legislation and the cybersecurity requirement established under the AI Act for high-risk AI systems support this point. With specific regard to art. 15(1) AI Act, one may perhaps claim that this provision inherently incorporates a value-laden requirement⁷⁰. The very same background of the AI Act, which is mostly framed as product safety legislation but with a view to pursuing fundamental rights protection, may pave the way for such construction. However, this provision does not operationalise nor substantiate such a thing as a fundamental right to cybersecurity. This does not prevent scholars from reflecting upon an augmented consideration of cybersecurity in digital policymaking, which will likely remain a pivotal issue in the coming years. But if the AI Act serves as a litmus test to measure the expansion of this concept beyond its well-established consideration, then it ultimately misses the opportunity to elevate cybersecurity to a fundamental rights concern.

⁷⁰ See among others A. Tartaro, *Value-laden challenges for technical standards supporting regulation in the field of AI*, cit.; M. Veale, *Value-Laden Areas for Standardisation in the AI Act*, 5 September 2022, at [michaeh](#); M. Cantero Gamito-C.T. Marsden, *Artificial intelligence co-regulation?*, cit.

Abstract

This paper explores the interplay between cybersecurity and artificial intelligence within the European Union's digital legislation. While cybersecurity has been seen as a tool to safeguard data protection, its emerging role suggests a broader regulatory ambition. The analysis investigates whether cybersecurity, as framed in the AI Act, may be transitioning toward a more autonomous legal status, possibly akin to a fundamental right. Through a doctrinal and normative assessment, the paper examines the tripartite role cybersecurity plays in the AI Act—as a non-functional requirement, a criterion for conformity assessment, and an organisational measure. Despite frequent references to cybersecurity and its conceptual proximity to data protection, the AI Act ultimately treats it within the confines of product safety legislation. The findings suggest that although cybersecurity is essential for AI system governance, its recognition as a fundamental right remains aspirational within the current EU legal landscape.

Keywords

artificial intelligence – AI Act – cybersecurity – Cyber Resilience Act – NIS2 Directive